

ISSUES OF STRENGTHENING THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN THE YOUTH IDEOLOGY

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Annotation: This article describes the corruption and its negative consequences, which is increasing all over the world in the era of globalization. Opinions were expressed that corruption harms the development of the state and society.

Key words: state and society, legal literacy, corruption, bribery and political consciousness.

Ensuring the supremacy of the law before the state and society, establishing justice, training competitive personnel at every level, and improving the quality of education are urgent topics. Preventing corruption in ensuring the transparency of these directions lays the groundwork for the key to development. The term corruption is a developed and popularized term, and it is considered to be understandable to everyone if we call it bribery and bribery in the vernacular. The Latin word corruption means "corruption". This is the use of authority and rights by some officials for their personal interests, contrary to the law and morality. The term corruption is mainly used within the political apparatus. Buying and selling officials for bribes is also considered corruption.

The head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, pays special attention to the fact that it is a first-class task to find a more widespread solution in our lives for the sense of justice, which our people value highly and put above all else. The President has taken strict measures to fight corruption, various crimes and other violations in our society, to prevent them, and to ensure that the law on the fact that punishment for crime is inevitable. "We need to reach out," he emphasized.

Adopted by the Legislative Chamber on November 24, 2016, approved by the Senate on December 13, 2016, by the President on December 3, 2017 The Law of

the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption" signed in January 2017 and entered into force on January 4, 2017 was an important step in this regard. Today, all countries are fighting against corruption. Each state and society chooses and fights for its own ways of fighting corruption. According to experts, the word corruption also means "selling". The historical roots of corruption go back to ancient times and it is believed to have originated from the practice of giving gifts to tribal chiefs in order to gain a certain position in the tribe. But the complexity and centralization of the state shows that corruption is a serious obstacle to the development of the state. The first country that fought against corruption was the Sumerian state. Ancient states were very worried about bribery. Because this situation has greatly worried the state's reputation. Because this situation would seriously damage the reputation of the state. Even in the world's leading religions, bribery of law enforcement agencies is strongly condemned. For example, in the book "Bible" it is said: "Do not accept gifts, because a gift makes the blind see and changes the truth", and in the Holy Qur'an it is said: "Do not take the property of others unjustly and "Don't bribe your governors from your property to get things that belong to others."

The analyzes show that the measures of state bodies are not enough to fight against corruption and prevent it, but strong cooperation of civil institutions is required and effective in this direction.

Civic institutions, non-governmental non-profit organizations are now becoming an important factor in the protection of democratic values, human rights and freedoms, and legal interests, they create conditions for citizens to realize their potential, to increase their social, socio-economic activity and legal culture, in society will help ensure the balance of interests.

Corruption is a terrible evil that afflicts the society in various ways. This vice undermines the principles of the rule of law, leads to the violation of human rights, hinders the functioning of markets, worsens the quality of life, and creates conditions for crime, terrorism and other bad events. This harmful phenomenon occurs in all

countries, regardless of whether they are big or small, rich or poor. Although effective efforts are being made by the world community to eliminate this harmful disease, it is still not eliminated. Factors causing corruption include: low legal literacy of the population - if the population does not know or understand the laws, it creates conditions for the official to use them for his personal interests. The damage caused by corruption is considered equal for all countries, it has a negative impact on reforms in the political, economic, social, and cultural aspects of the country and the reputation of the country in the international arena. Common types of corruption are bribery, fraud, extortion. If such crimes increase, distrust of citizens towards the state system will increase. Corruption, whether it is in the field of education, medicine or other fields, is equivalent to hitting the roots of society with an ax. Because a person who has knowledge and intelligence will never engage in corruption. He achieves his goal with his intelligence and hard work. Only ignorant and uneducated people can do such a thing. Because that's the only way to get a diploma. In this case, it is necessary to stop acquaintance relations. For example, if the teacher did not work on himself, but studied and got his diploma through acquaintance. Now, what kind of person will the children he brings up become in the future, after all, if he does not love and give love to his profession. Or let's say that a doctor, he studied and got a job with a bribe, then we will leave our health in whose hands. To the "businessmen" who follow only this money, property and father's reputation? No, such a society does not develop at all, on the contrary, it saws and destroys its own life roots. We need to increase mature, educated, talented, demanding and inquisitive young people in our society and open the way for them. Now we all encounter small manifestations of corruption in society. But it's good that now our country is trying to reduce such cases. If a person works honestly in his life, using his knowledge, energy, and creativity, such a person will not allow corruption and will understand the consequences.

Measures to fight against corruption and prevent crimes are systematically implemented in our country. Legal documents are adopted and implemented in the

areas that cause corruption factors in the life of the state and society. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 29, 2020 "On additional measures to improve the system of combating corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan" Anti-Corruption Agency was established for the purpose. International agreements on combating corruption of the Republic of Uzbekistan were signed with the UN Convention on Combating Corruption. Even though a number of measures are being taken to prevent corruption in our country, corruption-related crimes are still being committed by officials. To fight against corruption, it is necessary to raise the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population. Because people with a high level of legal consciousness and culture do not allow such negative vice-corruption. A sign of the strength of civil society is the responsibility of state bodies to the people. Fraud and abuse in the health care sector also show that corruption has taken root. In order to fight against corruption, it is necessary to improve the legal culture, identify and put an end to such cases as bribery, greed, and every person should know that punishment is applied against such crimes.

A person who learns to work properly and live honestly from a young age will have a happy life. He understands that injustice, disrespect for the law, betrayal of his profession and trust cannot be done, he has strength and confidence against bribery and corruption.

Young people will become courageous and conscientious people in the future. In any situation, an honest person wins in life and lives happily. Young people who have taken a bold step towards their actions and goals should make progress without corruption.

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